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Application of Solar Thermal Energy to Processes (ASTEP), Development and Demonstration

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ABSTRACT

This paper summarises the work being carried out under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 88441, Application of Solar Thermal Energy to Processes (ASTEP). The aim of this project is to develop a novel rotary Fresnel solar collector capable of supplying heat at 150° – 400°C in conjunction with a phase-change thermal store designed to operate at approximately 220°C. The collector rating is 25 kWth (nominal). The integrated systems will be demonstrated on two industrial sites: a dairy in Corinth, Greece and a metals processing plant in Iasi, Romania.

Two variants of the collector have been designed, constructed and tested in Madrid. One has single-axis tracking and is suitable for the latitudes of southern Europe, as represented by Corinth (38°N). The second has two-axis tracking to give improved performance at more northerly latitudes and will be tested in Iasi (47°N).

The thermal storage units which will be installed with the collectors on the industrial sites each comprise a vertical stainless steel cylinder 1m diameter and 1.6m high incorporating a serpentine tube with proprietary fins carrying thermal oil through the salt storage medium. The salt used is a eutectic mixture of KNO₃ and NaNO₃. Three stores have been manufactured and tested. Experimental results are in agreement with CFD analysis.

The ASTEP system for use in the dairy has been designed to produce steam and to power an absorption refrigerator, and the performance has been analysed on this basis. However initial on-site testing will be carried out applying a load simulating the demand of the dairy using an air-cooled heat exchanger. The system incorporated in the steel processing plant will be used to heat an oven in a purpose designed pilot plant heating steel tubes to simulate the requirement for heating prior to powder coating.